

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

RESULTS OF THE STUDY OF MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOLOGICAL TRAITS, AND NITROGEN-FIXING RHIZOBIUM BACTERIA IN LENTIL GENETIC RESOURCES DERIVED FROM THE ICARDA LENTIL COLLECTION UNDER DIFFERENT AGROECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This study, conducted during 2021–2024, presents the biological, morphological, and yield-related characteristics of lentil genetic resources evaluated under diverse ecological conditions in Armenia, with a focus on Ararat marz (Darakert) and Gegharkunik marz (Martuni).

Under the Darakert conditions, the lentil varieties Flip 2007-3L, Sellfrom 1767L, and Flip 2007-30L demonstrated superior performance compared with the control varieties. In Martuni, Flip 2007-12L, Flip 2007-30L, Sellfrom 1767L, EP-54, Flip 2007-3L, and Flip 2006-4L produced promising results.

Field studies conducted on lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) enabled a comprehensive assessment of agrochemical and biological changes in the soil and their effects on the intensity of symbiotic root nodule formation. The cultivars Flip 2006-4L, Flip 2007-30L, and EP-54 exhibited superior performance under both Darakert and Martuni agroecological conditions, promoting the formation of a higher number of nitrogen-fixing root nodules and thereby contributing to improved soil quality. These cultivars are recommended for further selection.

Keywords: Lentils, genetic resources, ecological conditions, biological and morphological characteristics, nodulation, soil analyses.

INTRODUCTION

Lentils (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) are among the earliest domesticated crops, dating back to approximately 7000 BC in the Fertile Crescent, a region extending from present-day Jordan to Turkey and southeastward to Iran. A substantial share of global lentil production still originates from this region. However, India and Canada are currently the largest producers, with nearly 60% of the world's lentil production concentrated in South Asia, including Bangladesh, Myanmar, India, Nepal, and Pakistan. Lentils are cultivated worldwide on approximately 1.8 million hectares [1]. In Bangladesh and Nepal, lentils represent the most important pulse crop for human consumption.

Globally, lentil production has increased steadily, more than tripling since 1982. The wild ancestor of cultivated lentil, *Lens culinaris* subsp. *orientalis*, closely resembles small-seeded cultivated forms and is characterized by pods that readily dehisce upon ripening. Early farmers selected for non-shattering pods, more erect plant architecture, and larger seeds with diverse coat colors as early as 7000 BC [2]. The genus *Lens* belongs to the family *Fabaceae* (*Leguminosae*), subfamily *Faboideae*, and tribe *Fabeae* (or subfamily *Papilionaceae*, tribe *Vicieae*). All species within the genus are diploid ($2n = 14$), annual, and predominantly self-pollinating, with a low rate of outcrossing [3].

Lentils comprise a wide range of cultivars adapted to diverse agroecological regions, exhibiting variation in nutrient composition, seed color, shape, and flavor. They are highly nutritious, providing substantial amounts of protein, vitamin A, dietary fiber, starch, potassium, B vitamins, and iron. Lentils are cholesterol-free, low in fat, and contain relatively low levels of anti-nutritional factors [4]. Beyond their

nutritional value, lentils offer important agronomic benefits. In regions such as the Middle East and North Africa, lentil straw serves as a valuable forage for small ruminants. Moreover, biological nitrogen fixation by rhizobial bacteria in lentil root nodules enhances soil fertility, contributing to sustainable agricultural systems [5].

Lentil breeding efforts have intensified since the late 1970s, resulting in significant improvements in yield potential and tolerance to abiotic stresses, particularly drought and cold. Genetic enhancement has also led to increased resistance to biotic stresses through the incorporation of traits from wild relatives and traditional landraces into modern high-yielding cultivars. Extensive lentil germplasm collections are conserved in gene banks worldwide, with the International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA) maintaining the global lentil gene pool [6].

In Armenia, lentil cultivation is currently limited to approximately 126 hectares, primarily located in Gegharkunik (34 ha), Shirak (55 ha), Kotayk (16 ha), Tavush (10 ha), Lori (10 ha), and Aragatsotn (1 ha), with an average yield of about 7.4 kg/ha (Fig. 1). Expansion of lentil cultivation and yield improvement in Armenia could be achieved through the development of new, high-yielding varieties adapted to the country's diverse agro-climatic conditions and suitable for mechanized harvesting. This study evaluates a global lentil collection to identify the most promising accessions for breeding and production under Armenian conditions

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was conducted between 2022 and 2024 in two distinct ecological regions of Armenia: the lowland zone of the Ararat Region (Darakert) and the mountainous zone of the Gegharkunik Region

(Martuni). A total of 100 lentil cultivars introduced from the International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA) were evaluated. From this collection, five large-seeded varieties—Flip 2007-12L, Flip 2007-30L, Sell from 1767L, EP-54, and Flip 2006-4L—were selected for further analysis. The variety Talin-6 was used as the control for the large-seeded group, while the Armenian-88 small-seeded variety served as the control for the small-seeded cultivar Flip 2007-3L.

Morphological characteristics of the cultivars were assessed according to the International Descriptor for Lentils [7]. Biochemical analyses were carried out at the Laboratory of Biotechnology, Phytopathology, and Biochemistry of the Scientific Centre. Soil samples collected before sowing and at the end of the growing season were analyzed and compared in relation to root nodule number and biomass. Soil NPK content was determined spectrophotometrically using a Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, USA).

The experimental data were subjected to statistical analysis using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significance of differences among the cultivars.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Height

Under Darakert conditions, the control cultivar Talini-6 exhibited a mean plant height of 38 cm. The highest value was recorded in Flip 2006-4L (48 cm), exceeding the control by 10 cm or 26.3%. Flip 2007-12L reached 45 cm, representing an increase of 18.4% compared with the control. Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 each attained a height of 44 cm, exceeding the control by 15.8%, while Flip 2007-30L reached 42 cm, corresponding to an increase of 10.5%.

In Martuni, the control cultivar Talini-6 had a mean plant height of 40 cm. The highest value was again observed in Flip 2006-4L (48 cm), which exceeded the control by 20.0%. Flip 2007-12L reached 45 cm (+12.5%), Sellfrom 1767L reached 42 cm (+5.0%), whereas EP-54 showed a value equal to the control.

Table 1. Morphological characteristics of lentil cultivars under varying climatic conditions (2022–2024 average).

Variety	Plant height, cm	Number of branches The height of the first pod, (cm)	The number of nodular bac- teria per plant, pcs	Weight of nodular bacteria per plant, g	Number of seeds per plant, pcs	Weight of seeds per plant, g	Number of pods per plant	Pod weight per plant, g	1000-grain weight	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Ararat region, Darakert										
Large-grain lentils										
Talini-6 control	38±1.2	5	16±1.1	5±1.5	0.4	100±1.4	4,2±1.5	75±2.3	6.1±0.8	44±1.3
Flip 2007- 12L	45±1.1	5	18±1.3	5±1.1	0.6	138±1.3	6.8±1.3	106±2.1	7.8±0.6	50±1.4
Sellfrom 1767L	44±1.3	5	13±1.2	5±1.4	0.6	128±1.1	6.9±1.4	98±2.5	7.8±0.3	45±1.3
Ep-54	44±1.2	4	16±1.3	6±1.2	0.5	111±1.3	6.9±1.3	81±1.1	6.8±0.3	44±1.2
Flip 2006-4L	48±1.8	5	18±1.2	8±1.1	0.7	147±1.4	6,6±1.4	106±2.5	7.5±0.2	50±1.3
Small-grain lentils										
Haykakan 88: Control	38±1.1	4	14±1.4	5±1.5	0.4	113±1.1	4.8±1.3	88±2.4	5.1±0.4	23±1.4
Flip 2007-3L	45±1.2	5	16±1.5	6±.3	0.5	154±1.5	8.2±1.2	120±2.5	8.8±0.2	28±1.5
Flip 2007- 30L	42±1.2	4	16±1.4	6±1.3	0.6	136±1.4	6.7±1.1	105±2.1	7.2±0.2	25±1.2
Gegharkunik region, Martuni										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Large-grain lentils										
Talin-6 ol	40±1.1	5	14	7±1.2	0,7	118±1.4	6.4±1.5	84±2.2	7.1±0.2	44±1.2
Flip 2007- 12L	45±1.3	5	18	10±1.1	1	133±1.3	7.6±2	120±2.4	8.2±0.3	48±2.2
Sellfrom 1767L	42±1.3	4	13	10±1.2	0,9	139±1.2	6.8±1.8	109±2.4	7.5±0.1	45±1.2
Ep-54	40±1.2	4	15	15±1.5	0,9	136±1.5	7.2±2.6	98±1.4	8.1±0.3	48±2.2
Flip 2006-4L	48±1.3	5	18	18±1.1	1,0	142±1.4	7.2±1.6	122±1.3	8.0±06	52±1.2
Small-grain lentils										
Haykakan 88: control	30±1.3	4	12	10±1.3	0,9	134±1.3	5.2±1.2	101±1.2	5.6±0.2	25±2.2
Flip 2007-3L	35±1.2	5	16	11±1.4	0,9	163±1.1	8.8±1.1	135±1.3	9.2±0.5	28.8±1.3
Flip 2007- 30L	42±1.4	5	12	10±1.3	1	141±1.3	7.3±1.5	114±2.3	7.6±0.7	30±3.0

Height of the First Pod

Under Darakert conditions, the first pod height of the control cultivar was 16 cm. The highest values were recorded in Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L (18 cm), exceeding the control by 12.5%. EP-54 showed a value equal to the control (16 cm), whereas Sellfrom 1767L recorded the lowest value (13 cm).

In Martuni, the control value was 14 cm. The highest first pod height was observed in Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L (18 cm), corresponding to an increase of 28.6% over the control. EP-54 reached 15 cm (+7.1%), while Sellfrom 1767L recorded 13 cm, slightly below the control.

Number of Nodules per Plant

Under Darakert conditions, the control cultivar formed an average of 5 nodules per plant. The highest nodulation was observed in Flip 2006-4L (8 nodules), representing a 60.0% increase compared with the control. EP-54 and Flip 2007-30L each produced 6 nodules (+20.0%), whereas Flip 2007-12L and Sellfrom 1767L did not differ from the control.

In Martuni, the control cultivar formed 7 nodules per plant. The highest value was recorded in Flip 2006-4L (18 nodules), exceeding the control by 157.1%. EP-54 produced 15 nodules (+114.3%), while Flip 2007-12L and Sellfrom 1767L each formed 10 nodules (+42.9%).

Nodule Weight per Plant

Under Darakert conditions, the control cultivar exhibited a mean nodule weight of 0.4 g per plant. The highest value was observed in Flip 2006-4L (0.7 g), which exceeded the control by 75.0%. Flip 2007-12L, Sellfrom 1767L, and Flip 2007-30L each recorded 0.6 g, representing an increase of 50.0%, whereas EP-54 reached 0.5 g (+25.0%).

In Martuni, the control value was 0.7 g per plant. The highest nodule weight was recorded in Flip 2006-4L, Flip 2007-12L, and Flip 2007-30L (1.0 g), corresponding to an increase of 42.9% relative to the control. Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 each recorded 0.9 g (+28.6%).

Number of Seeds per Plant

In Darakert, the control cultivar produced an average of 100 seeds per plant. The highest value was observed in Flip 2006-4L (147 seeds), exceeding the control by 47.0%. This was followed by Flip 2007-12L (138 seeds; +38.0%), Flip 2007-30L (136 seeds; +36.0%), Sellfrom 1767L (128 seeds; +28.0%), and EP-54 (111 seeds; +11.0%).

In Martuni, the control cultivar produced 118 seeds per plant. The highest seed number was again recorded in Flip 2006-4L (142 seeds), representing an increase of 20.3% over the control. Sellfrom 1767L produced 139 seeds (+17.8%), EP-54 produced 136

seeds (+15.3%), and Flip 2007-12L produced 133 seeds (+12.7%).

Seed Weight per Plant

Under Darakert conditions, the control cultivar exhibited a mean seed weight of 4.2 g per plant. The highest value was recorded in Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 (6.9 g), corresponding to an increase of 64.3% relative to the control. Flip 2007-12L produced 6.8 g (+61.9%), Flip 2007-30L produced 6.7 g (+59.5%), and Flip 2006-4L produced 6.6 g (+57.1%).

In Martuni, the control value was 6.4 g per plant. The highest seed weight was observed in Flip 2007-12L (7.6 g), exceeding the control by 18.8%. EP-54 and Flip 2006-4L each produced 7.2 g (+12.5%), while Sellfrom 1767L recorded 6.8 g (+6.3%).

Number of Pods per Plant

In Darakert, the control cultivar produced 75 pods per plant. The highest values were observed in Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L (106 pods), exceeding the control by 41.3%. Flip 2007-30L produced 105 pods (+40.0%), Sellfrom 1767L produced 98 pods (+30.7%), and EP-54 produced 81 pods (+8.0%).

In Martuni, the control value was 84 pods per plant. The highest pod number was recorded in Flip 2006-4L (122 pods), representing a 45.2% increase over the control. Flip 2007-12L produced 120 pods (+42.9%), Flip 2007-30L produced 114 pods (+35.7%), Sellfrom 1767L produced 109 pods (+29.8%), and EP-54 produced 98 pods (+16.7%).

Pod Weight per Plant

Under Darakert conditions, the control cultivar exhibited a pod weight of 6.1 g per plant. The highest values were recorded in Flip 2007-12L and Sellfrom 1767L (7.8 g), exceeding the control by 27.9%. Flip 2006-4L produced 7.5 g (+23.0%), Flip 2007-30L produced 7.2 g (+18.0%), and EP-54 produced 6.8 g (+11.5%).

In Martuni, the control value was 7.1 g per plant. The highest pod weight was observed in Flip 2007-12L (8.2 g), corresponding to an increase of 15.5% relative to the control. EP-54 produced 8.1 g (+14.1%), Flip 2006-4L produced 8.0 g (+12.7%), Flip 2007-30L produced 7.6 g (+7.0%), and Sellfrom 1767L produced 7.5 g (+5.6%).

1000-Seed Weight

In Darakert, the control cultivar exhibited a 1000-seed weight of 44 g. The highest values were recorded in Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L (50 g), exceeding the control by 13.6%. Sellfrom 1767L produced 45 g (+2.3%), while EP-54 was equal to the control (44 g).

In Martuni, the control value was 44 g. The highest 1000-seed weight was recorded in Flip 2006-4L (52 g), representing an increase of 18.2% over the control. Flip 2007-12L and EP-54 each produced 48 g (+9.1%), while Sellfrom 1767L recorded 45 g (+2.3%)

Table 2. Results of soil analyses from the Darakert and Martuni experimental fields in soils cultivated with different lentil varieties before sowing and at the end of the growing season. (2022–2024).

Samples	pH	EC, mS cm ⁻¹	Organic matter by C in dry matter, %	Nutrients available to plants, mg in 100 g of soil		
				N	P2O5	K2O
Ararat marz, Darakert						
Control(before sowing)	7,3	0,42	2,0	3,5	2,1	37,1
Talini 6(control)	7,2	0,42	2,2	3,6	2,2	37,7
Flip 2007- 12L	7,2	0,42	2,4	3,8	2,3	38,7
Flip 2007- 30L	7,1	0,42	2,4	3,9	2,4	38,4
Sellfrom 1767L	7,3	0,42	2,3	4,1	2,3	38,3
Ep-54	7,2	0,40	2,2	3,7	2,2	38,5
Flip 2006-4L	7,1	0,43	2,5	4,2	2,5	39,0
Haykakan 88 (control)	7,1	0,41	2,3	3,6	2,2	37,8
Flip 2007-3L	7,0	0,42	2,4	3,6	2,2	38,1
Gegarkunik marz, Martuni						
Control(before sowing)	7,1	0,43	5,8	6,3	3,0	25,0
Talini 6 (control.)	6,8	0,44	6,0	6,3	4,1	28,1
Flip 2007- 12L	6,5	0,43	6,2	6,5	5,7	29,8
Flip 2007- 30L	6,4	0,44	6,1	6,7	6,0	29,9
Sellfrom 1767L	6,4	0,44	6,0	6,7	6,0	29,0
Ep-54	6,5	0,43	6,3	6,5	4,9	28,5
Flip 2006-4L	6,5	0,44	6,4	6,6	6,5	29,9
Haykakan 88	7,0	0,43	6,0	6,7	6,2	29,1
Flip 2007-3L	6,8	0,45	6,6	6,8	6,3	29,2

Studies conducted in lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) experimental fields during 2022–2024 enabled a comprehensive assessment of agrochemical and biological changes occurring in the soil and their effects on the intensity of symbiotic root nodule formation. The analysis involved comparing soil samples collected before sowing and at the end of the growing season with indicators of nodule number and biomass.

One of the most important factors determining the productivity of leguminous crops and the improvement of soil fertility is symbiotic nitrogen fixation, which is mediated by nodule-forming bacteria of the genus *Rhizobium*. The effectiveness of this symbiosis depends not only on the genetic characteristics of the plant but also on the agrochemical and biological status of the soil (Graham & Vance, 2003; Peoples et al., 1995).

Soil Nutrients and Root Nodule Formation

Studies in Darakert and Martuni experimental fields revealed that soil agrochemical properties strongly influenced the number and biomass of nitrogen-fixing root nodules.

In Darakert, the initial soil status was characterized by low nitrogen (3.57 mg/100 g), medium phosphorus and potassium, and limited organic matter (2.0%). By the end of the growing season, treatments with Flip 2006-4L and Sellfrom 1767L showed the largest improvements, with nitrogen increasing to 4.1–4.2 mg/100 g, organic matter to 2.5%, and significant increases in nodule formation. Flip 2006-4L recorded the highest nodulation (8 ± 2 nodules; 0.7 g biomass), exceeding the control (5 ± 2 nodules; 0.4 g). Soil pH

remained near neutral (7.1–7.3) and EC stable (0.40–0.43 mS cm⁻¹), providing a favorable, non-saline environment for nodulation. Limited organic matter in Darakert likely constrained nodule development compared to Martuni.

In Martuni, initial soil fertility was higher, with total nitrogen of 6.3 mg/100 g and organic matter of 7.1%. By season's end, treatments showed increased nutrients: nitrogen up to 6.8 mg/100 g, phosphorus to 6.5 mg/100 g, and organic matter to 6.6%. Correspondingly, root nodule formation was more intensive. Flip 2006-4L again had the highest nodulation (13 ± 2 nodules; 1.0 g biomass), followed by EP-54 (12 ± 2 nodules; 0.9 g) and Flip 2007-30L (10 ± 2 nodules; 0.9 g). Soil pH (6.4–7.1) and low EC (0.43–0.45 mS cm⁻¹) were optimal for *Rhizobium* activity, explaining the higher symbiotic efficiency relative to Darakert.

Comparative analysis shows a clear relationship: higher soil fertility and organic matter levels correlate with greater nodule number and biomass. Treatments with limited nutrient improvements (e.g., Talin-6 and Haykakan 88 controls) showed only modest increases in nodulation.

Conclusion: Soil nutrient enrichment—particularly nitrogen, phosphorus, and organic matter—along with favorable pH, is critical for enhancing root nodule formation and symbiotic nitrogen fixation. Among the cultivars tested, Flip 2006-4L and Flip 2007-3L were the most effective and are recommended for improving lentil productivity under varying Armenian agroecological conditions.

Table 3. Biological properties of lentils in different agroecological conditions 2022-2024

Variety	Regions	Sowing date	From sowing to germination, days	From germination to, days	
				Flowering	seed ripening
Talini-6 Control	*1	28.04	7	54	105
	**2	08.05	10	62	115
Flip 2007-12L	*1	28.04	5	54	100
	**2	08.05	10	62	112
Sellfrom 1767L	*1	28.04	5	50	95
	**2	08.05	8	46	105
Ep-54	*1	28.04	7	52	95
	**2	08.05	7	49	105
Flip 2006-4L	*1	28.04	6	47	105
	**2	08.05	6	65	113
Armenian 88: Control	*1	28.04	6	56	105
	**2	08.05	8	65	115
Flip 2007-3L	*1	28.04	5	53	102
	**2	08.05	6	58	112
Flip 2007-30L	*1	28.04	5	53	110
	**2	08.05	16	51	122

*1 - Ararat Region, **2- Gegharkunik Region **Biological Traits of Lentil Cultivars Germination Period:**

Germination Period

Under the agroecological conditions of the Ararat region (Darakert), the period from sowing to germination ranged from 5 to 7 days. The shortest germination period was recorded in the varieties Sellfrom 1767L, Flip 2007-12L, Flip 2007-3L, and Flip 2007-30L, which germinated within 5 days, representing a 28.6% reduction compared with the control cultivar Talini-6 (7 days). Flip 2006-4L germinated within 6 days (14.3% earlier than the control), while EP-54 showed a germination period equal to that of the control.

In the Gegharkunik region (Martuni), germination occurred within 6–16 days. The earliest emergence was observed in Flip 2006-4L and Flip 2007-3L, which germinated within 6 days, corresponding to a 40.0% reduction relative to the control cultivar Talini-6 (10 days). EP-54 germinated within 7 days (30.0% earlier), while Sellfrom 1767L and the control cultivar Haykakan 88 germinated within 8 days. Flip 2007-12L showed a germination period equal to the control, whereas Flip 2007-30L exhibited the longest germination period (16 days), exceeding the control by 60.0%.

Flowering Time

In the Ararat region, the duration from germination to flowering ranged from 47 to 56 days. Among the large-seeded genotypes, the earliest flowering was recorded in Flip 2006-4L (47 days), which flowered 13.0% earlier than the control cultivar Talini-6 (54 days). Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 flowered after 50 and 52 days, representing reductions of 7.4% and 3.7%, respectively. Flip 2007-12L flowered simultaneously with the control. Among the small-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-3L and Flip 2007-30L reached flowering after 53 days, which was 5.4% earlier than the control cultivar Haykakan 88 (56 days).

In the Gegharkunik region, flowering occurred within 46–65 days after germination. The earliest flowering was observed in Sellfrom 1767L (46 days), representing a 25.8% reduction compared with the control cultivar Talini-6 (62 days). EP-54 flowered after 49 days (21.0% earlier), while Flip 2007-30L and

Flip 2007-3L flowered after 51 and 58 days, respectively. The latest flowering was recorded in Flip 2006-4L and Haykakan 88, both requiring 65 days to reach flowering.

Seed Ripening

Under Darakert conditions, seed ripening occurred within 95–110 days after germination. The earliest maturity was recorded in Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54, both reaching seed ripening after 95 days, corresponding to a 9.5% reduction relative to the control cultivar Talini-6 (105 days). Flip 2007-12L matured after 100 days (4.8% earlier than the control), while Flip 2007-3L required 102 days. The latest maturity was observed in Flip 2007-30L, which reached seed ripening after 110 days.

In the Gegharkunik region, the ripening period ranged from 105 to 122 days. The earliest seed ripening among the large-seeded genotypes was recorded in Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54, both maturing after 105 days, which was 8.7% earlier than the control cultivar Talini-6 (115 days). Flip 2007-12L reached maturity after 112 days (2.6% earlier), while Flip 2006-4L matured after 113 days. Among the small-seeded genotypes, the control cultivar Haykakan 88 reached maturity after 115 days, whereas Flip 2007-3L matured after 112 days (2.6% earlier). The longest growing period was recorded in Flip 2007-30L, which required 122 days to reach seed ripening.

Summary

The obtained results demonstrated considerable variation among lentil genotypes in the duration of major developmental stages under different agroecological conditions. In the Ararat region, Sellfrom 1767L, EP-54, and Flip 2006-4L were characterized by earlier flowering and seed ripening compared with the control cultivars. In the Gegharkunik region, Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 exhibited the earliest flowering and maturity, indicating good adaptation to cooler highland conditions. Flip 2007-3L also showed relatively early development among the small-seeded genotypes. Conversely, Flip 2007-30L displayed a prolonged vegetation period, particularly under Gegharkunik conditions, where both

germination and seed ripening were considerably delayed. Overall, Sellfrom 1767L and EP-54 demonstrated the most stable earliness across both

ecological regions and may be considered promising sources for breeding and cultivation programs aimed at developing early-maturing lentil varieties in Armenia.

Table 4. Economically valuable characteristics of lentils under different ecological conditions (3-year average) 2022-2024

Variety	Regions	Average yield, centners/ha	Difference from the control	
			centners/ha	%
Talini-6 Control	1	18.8	-	-
	2	22.0	-	-
Flip 2007 -12L	1	22.5	3.7	19.7
	2	28.6	6.6	30
Sellfrom 1767L	1	24.5	5.7	30.3
	2	26.0	4.0	18.1
Ep-54	1	26.0	7.2	41.4
	2	27.2	5.2	32.2
Flip 2006-4L	1	21.0	2.2	11.7
	2	28.0	6	41
Haykakan88: Control	1	19.6	-	-
	2	21.3	-	-
Flip 2007-3L	1	29.0	9.4	48
	2	31.0	9.7	45
Flip 2007-30L	1	25.0	6.2	33
	2	27.3	5.3	33.2
LSD 0.05		1.3		

1 - Ararat Region, 2- Gegharkunik Region

Economically Valuable Traits: Yield Performance

The three-year average grain yield of lentil genotypes varied considerably between the Ararat and Gegharkunik regions, reflecting differences in both genetic potential and environmental adaptation.

In the Ararat Region (Darakert), the yield of the control cultivar Talini-6 was 18.8 centners ha⁻¹, while the control cultivar Haykakan 88 produced 19.6 centners ha⁻¹. Among the large-seeded genotypes, the highest yield was recorded in EP-54 (26.0 centners ha⁻¹), exceeding the control Talini-6 by 7.2 centners ha⁻¹ or 41.4%. Sellfrom 1767L yielded 24.5 centners ha⁻¹, representing an increase of 30.3%, whereas Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L produced 22.5 and 21.0 centners ha⁻¹, exceeding the control by 19.7% and 11.7%, respectively.

Among the small-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-3L exhibited the highest productivity, producing 29.0 centners ha⁻¹ and surpassing the control cultivar Haykakan 88 by 9.4 centners ha⁻¹ or 48.0%. Flip 2007-30L also demonstrated high yield potential, producing 25.0 centners ha⁻¹, which was 6.2 centners ha⁻¹ or 33.0% higher than the control Talini-6 and 27.6% higher than Haykakan 88.

In the Gegharkunik Region (Martuni), overall yields were higher than those obtained in the Ararat Region. The control cultivar Talini-6 yielded 22.0 centners ha⁻¹, whereas Haykakan 88 produced 21.3 centners ha⁻¹.

Among the large-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-12L achieved the highest yield (28.6 centners ha⁻¹), exceeding the control Talini-6 by 6.6 centners ha⁻¹ or 30.0%. Flip 2006-4L yielded 28.0 centners ha⁻¹ (+27.3%), EP-54 produced 27.2 centners ha⁻¹ (+23.6%), and Sellfrom 1767L yielded 26.0 centners ha⁻¹ (+18.1%).

Among the small-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-3L again exhibited the highest productivity, producing 31.0 centners ha⁻¹, which exceeded the control cultivar Haykakan 88 by 9.7 centners ha⁻¹ or 45.0%. Flip 2007-30L yielded 27.3 centners ha⁻¹, representing an increase of 6.0 centners ha⁻¹ or 28.2% compared with Haykakan 88.

The results indicate that the yield superiority of the investigated genotypes was consistent across contrasting ecological conditions. In particular, Flip 2007-3L, EP-54, Flip 2007-12L, Flip 2006-4L, and Flip 2007-30L demonstrated stable and high productivity in both regions, highlighting their broad adaptation and potential value for lentil breeding and cultivation programs.

The observed yield differences exceeded the least significant difference (LSD_{0.05} = 1.3 centners ha⁻¹), indicating that the advantages of the superior genotypes over the control cultivars were statistically significant.

Summary

Evaluation of lentil genotypes under the agroecological conditions of the Ararat and Gegharkunik regions revealed substantial variation in growth, development, biological traits, and grain productivity. In general, the Gegharkunik region provided more favorable conditions for lentil cultivation, resulting in higher values for most economically important traits, including plant height, number of nodules, seed production, and grain yield.

Among the large-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-12L, EP-54, and Flip 2006-4L consistently exhibited superior agronomic performance. These genotypes combined high seed and pod productivity with favorable nodulation characteristics and stable grain yields across both environments. Sellfrom 1767L was distinguished by its early flowering and maturity,

indicating strong adaptation to environments with shorter growing seasons.

Among the small-seeded genotypes, Flip 2007-3L demonstrated the highest overall productivity. This genotype produced the greatest grain yield in both regions and exhibited favorable values for seed number, seed weight, and pod production. Flip 2007-30L also showed high yield potential, although its growing season was relatively longer, particularly under Gegharkunik conditions.

Overall, the results identified Flip 2007-3L, Flip 2007-12L, EP-54, and Flip 2006-4L as the most promising genotypes for lentil production under diverse agroecological conditions of Armenia.

Conclusion

The comparative evaluation of lentil genotypes conducted during 2022–2024 demonstrated significant differences in biological development, yield components, and grain productivity under the agroecological conditions of the Ararat and Gegharkunik regions.

In the Ararat Region, the highest grain yield among large-seeded genotypes was obtained from EP-54 (26.0 centners ha⁻¹), while Flip 2007-3L achieved the highest productivity among all tested genotypes (29.0 centners ha⁻¹). In the Gegharkunik Region, Flip 2007-12L and Flip 2006-4L were the most productive large-seeded genotypes, whereas Flip 2007-3L again recorded the highest grain yield (31.0 centners ha⁻¹).

The genotypes Flip 2007-12L, EP-54, Flip 2006-4L, and Flip 2007-3L were characterized by favorable combinations of agronomic traits, including increased plant height, higher first pod placement, improved nodulation capacity, greater numbers of pods and seeds per plant, and enhanced grain yield. Sellfrom 1767L was distinguished by earlier flowering and maturity, suggesting its suitability for breeding programs focused on earliness.

Based on the obtained results, Flip 2007-3L, Flip 2007-12L, EP-54, and Flip 2006-4L are recommended as promising sources of valuable traits for lentil improvement and as potential cultivars for cultivation under different agroclimatic conditions of Armenia. Their stable performance and high productivity indicate substantial potential for increasing lentil production and improving the sustainability of cropping systems.

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